

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Arabinose and Xylose by Iodine in Alkaline Solutions

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Iodine has invariably been used in the oxidation of reducing sugars in alkaline media¹. In these oxidations the aldose sugars are oxidised directly to their corresponding aldonic acids. Kinetic investigations of the oxidation of reducing sugars with iodine in alkaline solution have been reported by many workers². Iodine dissolved in alkaline solution gives various oxidising species (HOI, OI⁻, I₃⁻ and IO₃⁻ ions) in the system. The literature on the kinetics of the oxidation of reducing sugars by iodine in alkaline solution appears to be scanty. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation of iodine oxidation of arabinose and xylose in the presence of alkaline solution for understanding the mechanism of the oxidation of these sugars by iodine in alkaline solution.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 reveals that order of reaction with respect to iodine concentration is zero. However, the reaction velocity gradually decreases in the latter part of the reaction. Table 1 data show that the reaction has first order dependence on arabinose and

xylose concentrations. The results of the effect of pH (Table 2) or the rate of oxidation show that reaction rate was maximum in the vicinity of pH 11.00 and decreases on either side of the range.

Hence, order of the reaction with respect to iodite ion is supposed to be unity for explaining the observed kinetic orders. The plot of rate of oxidation versus pH was found to be identical with the plot of [OI⁻] vs pH in each case. The high

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF k_s WITH CHANGE IN CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATES

Arabinose : [I ₂] = 5.00 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , pH = 10.10, Temp. = 298 K		Xylose : [I ₂] = 4.30 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , pH = 9.60, Temp. = 298 K			
10 ⁴ [Arabinose] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	10 ⁴ [Xylose] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
1.00	1.20	1.20	0.87	1.32	1.52
1.50	1.70	1.16	1.74	2.59	1.49
2.00	2.40	1.20	2.61	3.81	1.46
2.50	3.00	1.20	3.48	5.18	1.49
3.00	3.60	1.20	4.35	6.39	1.47
3.50	4.20	1.20	—	—	—

Fig. 1. Plots of [I₂] vs time for (a) arabinose and (b) xylose; [Arabinose] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Xylose] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 298 K, pH = 10.10.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF VARIOUS EXPERIMENTS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF HYPOIODOUS ACID AT DIFFERENT pH

[Arabinose]= 7.50×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[I₂]= 5.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, Temp.=298 K
[Xylose]= 16.66×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[I₂]= 8.50×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, Temp.=303 K

Arabinose			Xylose		
pH	10 ⁴ × [HOI] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ × k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	pH	10 ⁴ × [HOI] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
9.70	0.20	4.18	10.10	4.78	8.00
10.40	1.90	7.98	10.80	5.50	8.50
10.60	2.70	8.00	11.00	8.40	9.10
10.80	4.00	15.10	11.30	12.50	24.80
11.20	7.40	27.20	11.80	11.60	22.10
11.80	7.90	7.46	12.20	6.60	14.10
12.20	5.30	6.70	12.30	5.90	11.20
12.40	4.00	2.00	—	—	—

value of free energy of activation (Table 3) suggests that transition state is highly solvated. The high negative value of entropy of activation indicates that there is greater degree of freedom of molecules in the transition state as compared to that in the reactive species.

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON REACTION RATE

[Arabinose]= 5.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[I₂]= 5.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH=9, 7, Temp.=298 K
[Xylose]= 25.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³,
[I₂]= 12.50×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH=9.4, Temp.=298 K

Arabinose			Xylose		
Temp. K	10 ⁴ 1/T	10 ⁴ × k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	Temp. K	10 ⁴ 1/T	10 ⁴ × k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
293	34.13	5.51	293	34.13	7.00
298	33.56	7.98	298	33.56	8.50
303	33.02	11.02	303	33.02	14.00
308	32.46	14.98	308	32.46	17.00
313	31.97	—	313	31.97	21.00
Substrate	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	
Arabinose	45.42	43.32	-83.67	68.12	
Xylose	42.30	40.81	-85.43	66.32	

Table 4 data indicate no salt-effect on the reaction rate. Hence, it is concluded that the rate-determining step must involve neutral molecules.

Now, it is quite likely that under experimental conditions, the oxidant and substrate exist in the forms of OI⁻ and S respectively.

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF k_s WITH THE CHANGE IN IONIC STRENGTH OF THE MEDIUM

[Arabinose]= 5.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [I₂]= 5.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH=10.10, Temp.=303 K
[Xylose]= 25.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [I₂]= 12.50×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH=9.30, Temp.=298 K

Arabinose		Xylose	
10 ³ [KCl] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	10 ³ [KCl] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _s mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.00	8.60	0.00	6.65
8.33	7.60	6.00	5.85
16.66	8.10	16.00	6.00
24.99	8.30	20.00	5.00
33.32	8.50	—	—

Negligible salt-effect was observed.

Based on the steps (1) and (2), the rate law (3) has been deduced,

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d[OI^-]}{dt} &= \frac{K_1 k_2 [S][OI^-]_T}{(K_{-1} + k_2) + K_1 [S]} \\ &= \frac{K_1 k_2 [S][OI^-]_T}{K_{-1} + k_2} \end{aligned}$$

assuming $K_{-1} + k_2 \gg K_1 [S]$ or, $=K[S][OI^-]_T$ (3)

The results of the Tables 1 and 2 and the straight line plots (not shown) of k_s vs [Arabinose]/[Xylose] are in conformity with the rate law (3). It is concluded that in alkaline media OI⁻ is the reactive species of iodine and maximum oxidation takes place in the vicinity of pH 11.00.

Experimental

Reagents used were of A.R. grade (B.D.H., E. Merck). For the purpose of present study, 0.1 M solutions of arabinose, xylose (Loba) and iodine (in KI) were prepared. The requisite volumes of buffer solutions of desired pH and the substrates were maintained at the desired temperature. To the mixture were added required volume of iodine solution which too was maintained at the temperature of the reaction. The kinetic procedure employed was the same as reported earlier³. Reproducible results were obtained.

The estimation of unconsumed iodine from different sets of experiments with various iodine to arabinose and xylose ratios indicated consumption of one mole of iodine per mole of the substrate.

References

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